

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) in ichnology

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Abstract

I observed the ichnofabric variable on 600 ichnofabric units in the Samarinda area of Kutai Basin. Five ichnofabric variables are bioturbation index (BI), biodiversity (ID), number of behaviors (NB), penetration depth (PD), and burrow diameter (DM) that perform as a semi-quantitative form. It must process the data with principal component analysis (PCA) to extract useful information from the data. Results of the PCA are the new principal components (PC), the loading of the ichnofabric variables in the PC-1 and PC-2, and the scattered pattern of the ichnofabric unit scores in PC-1 PC-2 axes. PC-1 has a "strong" positive correlation with ID and NB, a "moderate" positive correlation with BI, and a "weak" positive correlation with PD and DM. In contrast, the PC-2 correlates positively with BI, PD, and DM and correlates negatively with ID and NB. The PC-2 correlates moderately with PD and DM and correlates weakly with BI, ID, and NB. The dispersion pattern of the ichnofabric unit scores on PC-1 and PC-2 axes shown no simple pattern. PC-1 and PC-2 are interpreted as ichnodisparity and space utilization, respectively. The results of the PCA might be the unique indicators for a Miocene brackish depositional system in the study area. The application of PCA in this study has helped to know that the sediment source comes from land and the sea (tides and waves).

Introduction

In ichnofabric studies, I need semi-quantitative data to study deposition systems (Arifullah et al. 2021). Analysis of significant components (PCA) has been widely applied. I applied it in ichnology (e.g., Arifullah et al. 2017, 2018, 2019; Arifullah, 2019), paleoecology (Van der Zwan and Jorissen, 1991), hydrogeology (Liu et al. 2003).

An enormous amount of data with over two-variable needs data processing, making it easier for further data analysis. This is because not all data variables are needed. Usually, several variables are discarded and maintain others. This way is subjective. The aim is to allow the data set to reveal the weight of its relevant variable. For this reason, I use principal component analysis (PCA). With PCA, the semi-quantitative ichnofabric variable (Arifullah, 2019; Arifullah et al. 2021) can be reduced to two components that group the ichnofabric variable.

Data and Method

The basis data for PCA were the observed 600 ichnofabric units in the Serravallian-Tortonian sequence of Kutai Basin, East Kalimantan, Indonesia (Figure 1). Each ichnofabric unit had five ichnofabric variables, i.e., bioturbation index (BI), ichnodiversity (ID), number of behavior (NB), penetration depth (PD), and burrow diameter (DM) in numerical form (see in Arifullah, 2019).

I assumed the five ichnofabric variables as the five axes in the Cartesian coordinate system. The problem was how to draw those axes and how to visualize the point of ichnofabric unit do. Were those variables critical? If only some parts were necessary, several variables must be maintained, and others must be discarded. However, it was

Figure 1. Geological map of Samarinda Area, Indonesia (modified after Supriatna et al. 1995). Reprinted with permission from the Geological Agency, Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources of Indonesia.

a subjective approach. The aim approach was to allow the data to reveal its variable weights. PCA permits me to keep the original data and simplify them into 2 or 3 dimensions without reducing the original structure significantly. That 2 or 3 dimensions were the new coordinate axes that called principal components (PC). In addition, PAST-4 was the free software that helps with PCA.

Since BI, ID, NB, PD, and DM are in different units, I standardized them (Arifullah et al. 2017, Arifullah, 2019). There are two ways for standardization. First, by statistics formula and the second by transforming the continuous value (i.e., PD and DM) to discrete one (see Table 2 and 3 in Arifullah et al. 2021). I created a Pareto histogram that ranks the PCs with the highest% cumulative frequency to the lowest one. The x-axis represents the principal component (PC) comprising PC-1, PC-2, PC-3, PC-4, PC-5. There are two y-axes on the axis that describe the PC's eigenvalue and cumulative frequency percentage. The

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purpose of having an axis showing the cumulative frequency presentation of PCs is to determine a 60% cutoff with precision to determine a representative PC as directed by Jolliffe (2002).

I choose the principal component based on a 60% to 90% cutoff of cumulative variance (Jolliffe, 2002), and the principal components should have a minimum eigenvalue of 1 (Kaiser, 1960). The first principal component is PC-1, the second principal component is PC-1, the third principal component is PC-3, etc. The eigenvalue of PC-1 > PC-2 > PC-3 > PC-n and so on. If the eigenvalue is the value that shows how the power of PC to spreading of data, then PC-1 is more powerful than PC-2, and PC-2 is more potent than PC-3, and so on.

The new PC had ichnofabric variables with a different weight of contribution that was shown by coefficient correlation value. If coefficient correlation index > 0,75, 0,75 to 0,5 and 0,5 to 0,3, then represent "strong", "medium" and "weak" correlation respectively to PC (see Liu et al. 2003).

Result

Principal components

If the cumulative frequency curve cuts the 60% cutoff line from the y-axis, then only PC-1 and PC-2 are qualified to represent all existing PCs (Figure 2). The cumulative frequency is 62.40%, while the remaining 37.6% is the cumulative frequency of PC-3, PC-4, and PC-5. Likewise, if based on the eigenvalues, PC-1 and PC-2 are 2 of 5 PCs with an eigenvalue of over 1, i.e., 1.87 and 1.25. Thus, PC-1 and PC-2 are priorities to be discussed further in this paper.

PCA helps me learn and understand the interrelationship between five ichnofabric variables (i.e., BI, ID, NB, PD, and DM). The interrelationship between BI, ID, NB, PD, and DM variables to the PC-1 and PC-2 can be from the different correlation coefficients (Figure 3). Based on the strength of the correlation, PC-1 has a "strong" correlation with ID and NB, a "moderate" correlation with BI, and a "weak" correlation with PD and DM. In contrast, PC-2 correlates positively with BI, PD, and DM and negatively correlates with ID and NB. Based on the strength of the correlation, PC-2 correlated "moderately" with PD and DM and "weak" with BI, ID, and NB. Thus PC-1 represents the BI, ID, and

Figure 2. Pareto histogram of PCs. Each PC shows its eigenvalue and cumulative frequency (Arifullah, 2019).

Figure 3. The relationship between ichnofabric variables (BI, ID, NB, PD, and DM) with PC-1 and PC-2 (Arifullah, 2019).

NB, and PC-2 represents PD and DM. The next task is to find out what variables PC-1 and PC-2 are.

Ichnofabric units score and scattered diagram

As already mentioned, each of the ichnofabric units has the values of the ichnofabric variable (i.e., BI, ID, NB, PD, and DM). Each of the ichnofabric variables has a different load in each PC-1 and PC-2. Thus, each ichnofabric unit has a value on PC-1 and PC-2, referred to as a score. Since I studied 600 ichnofabric units, there are 600 x 2 PC = 1200 scores, as exemplified in Table 1. The scatter diagram shows the relationship between PC-1 and PC-2 measured in the same ichnofabric units (Figure 4). The dots in the scatter diagram represent ichnofabric units. Figure 4 displays a scatter diagram, and the type of relation between PC-1 and PC-2 implies a no linear relation ($r = 0,000$).

Table 1. Examples of tabulations showing PC-1 and PC-2 scores in each ichnofabric unit (Arifullah, 2019).

N	Ichnofabric unit	PC-1 score	PC-2 score
1	01-Op-07	0,28	1,32
2	01-Ch-03	1,34	0,66
3	01-Pa-03	0,47	0,41
4	01-Ch-04	-1,14	1,03
5	01-Op-08	-1,43	-0,36
....
600	16-Sk-05	-1,62	-1,28

Figure 4. The scatter diagram shows the relationship between PC-1 and PC-2 measured in the same ichnofabric units. The dots in the diagram represent ichnofabric units (Arifullah, 2019). Type of relation between PC-1 and PC-2 implies a no linear relation ($r = 0,000$).

Discussion

The strength of PCA

PCA allows us to study and understand the depositional system, helping the geologist see in two PC that otherwise would have to be seen in over five variables (i.e., BI, ID, NB, PD, and DM) to be studied. I can consider PCA the best technique to approach any semi-quantitative data. PCA is a handy tool for dealing with some problems with fluvial-marine transition depositional systems.

In that system, I respect the environmental variables which regulate the ichnofabric variable. In reality, complicated interrelationships happen in this depositional system, including positive and negative feedback loops. However, PCA makes it simpler to understand. The five ichnofabric variables (i.e., BI, ID, NB, PD, and DM) are reduced become two components (i.e., PC-1 and PC-2).

Paleoecology

BI, ID, and NB suggest innovation, mobility, and fauna behavior (Arifullah, 2019) which Buatois and Mángano (2013) called ichnodisparity. Thus, PC-1 represents ichnodisparity (Arifullah, 2019). PD and DM show a positive correlation with the larger size of the fauna, followed by increasing the penetration depth (Arifullah, 2019). Referring to Levinton (1977) and Reise (1979), then PC-2 is a component of space utilization. If referring to Fig.3, then the PC-1 axis is ichnodisparity and PC-2 is space utilization.

Since the food resources are a common factor considered in the ecological analysis (Bambach, 1983), then the ichnodisparity reflects the factor food supply. A particular mechanism supplies food to the ecosystem. Since the interaction of fluvial and marine processes in the basin (Bachtiar, 2003; Arifullah, 2005; Arifullah, 2019), the food supply is from land and marine (Van Der Zwaan and Jorissen, 1991; Brenckley and Harper, 1998). Food is supplied as seston, bound to sediment grains (Brenckley and Harper, 1998).

The component of space utilization reflects paleosalinity and paleotemperature fluctuation in the depositional system. There is an interaction between the fluvial processes and the origin of the sea in the Kutai Basin. The fluctuating salinity and temperature are general conditions in a brackish environment (Dalrymple and Choi, 2007; Buatois and Mangano, 2011).

Depositional processes

The question is the meaning of the scatter diagram, and the type of relation implies a nonlinear relationship. There is no relationship between ichnodisparity and space utilization or no linear relationship between food supply and paleosalinity-paleotemperature fluctuation. Thus, food supply and paleosalinity-paleotemperature fluctuation can be directly proportional or inversely proportional. If the food supply from land increases, there will be a decrease in paleosalinity and paleotemperature fluctuation.

On the one hand, if the food supply of land origin increases, there will be an increase in paleosalinity and

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paleotemperature fluctuation. Thus, the food supply can cause an increase and decrease in paleosalinity-paleotemperature fluctuation. I interpreted if food supply as a fluvial input function, then it is natural that fluvial inputs increase, then there will be a decrease in paleosalinity-paleotemperature fluctuation. However, what happened was precisely an uncommon thing. So, I interpret that food supply comes from land and the sea (tides and waves).

The existence of both inputs shows the fluvial process, and the process of sea origin modifies each other's deposition system in Serravallian-Tortonian intervals. The interaction of fluvial processes and ocean origin forms a delta or estuary or both at once. What is interesting here is that ichnofossil can determine the proportion of fluvial processes and processes of ocean origin (tides and waves).

Conclusions

Results derived from PCA present an actual picture of paleoecology and depositional processes of the Serravallian-Tortonian fluvial-marine transition zone with no data manipulation. PCA may help me to interpret the paleoecology and depositional processes easily.

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